

Numerical analysis of displacements in circular discs applied with different materials

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Abstract: Displacement (displacement) is the ejection of the disc relative to its normal position. In this study; Radial displacements from the inner surface to the outer surface of discs consisting of Tungsten carbide (WC), Boron carbide (B4C), Silicon Carbide (SSiC), Silicon Nitride (Si3N4) and Carbon Glass Fiber exposed to linear decreasing temperature distributions (displacement) has been analyzed analytically. The displacement values obtained for the temperatures of 30° C, -45° C, -60° C, -75° C, -90° C and -105° C were shared with the graphics. It is assumed that there will be no change in the elasticity modulus of the material with the temperature. As a result of the study, it was concluded that significant changes may occur in the displacement (displacement) values with the temperature changes, and the displacements they show against the temperature are different from each other according to the difference in the mechanical properties of the materials.

Key words: Modulus of elasticity, displacements, Tungsten carbide (WC), Boron carbide (B4C), Silicon Carbide (SSiC), Silicon Nitride (Si3N4) and Carbon Glass Fiber

1. Introduction

Temperature directly affects the material characteristics. The behavior of each material against temperature is different from each other. Temperature changes can trigger unwanted problems and permanent damage in machines. For these reasons, it is very important to investigate the effect of temperature on machine parts. When the literature search is done; In general, it was observed that radial and tangential stresses were determined in discs made up of different materials. For example; In a study, the thermal elastic stress analysis under parabolic varying temperatures from the inner surface to the outer surface of the orthotropic rotating perforated disc was analyzed analytically. The obtained results have been shared with the literature [1]. In another study; Linear elastic stresses of hollow cylinder and rotating disk problems with functionally graded materials have been investigated [2]. In one of two different studies; Stresses occurring in a boron carbide (B4C) disc were investigated by taking certain temperatures as reference. In the other study; Radial and tangential stresses of discs of different diameters modeled from Aluminum (Al2024-T3) - Boron Carbide (B4c) were investigated. The findings obtained were shared with the literature [3, 4]. In another study; Investigation of Elastic Tensile Behavior of Thermoplastic Discs Reinforced With Steel Wires [5]. Performing thermal stress analysis by applying the finite element method is highly preferred in academic studies and the good results are shared with the literature. For example; In a study; A Galerkin finite element method is used to find the numerical solution of the Newell-Whitehead Segel equation, which is a nonlinear parabolic partial differential equation. Numerical

results were shared with graphics [6]. In another study; Producer and Consumer Quality Levels for QSSSS-2 through Numerical Methods and Weighted Poisson Distribution were investigated [7]. In a different study; Designing of Skip lot sampling plan (SkSP-3) with Single Sampling Plan as reference plan under the conditions of Intervened Poisson distribution has been investigated [8]. Three-dimensional stress analysis of the brake disc-lining mechanism was performed and it was concluded that temperature could directly affect the stresses [9]. In a different study; Based on Mindlin's theory, the stresses occurring in thermoelastic rotating discs have been investigated [10]. In general, it has been observed that the radial and tangential stresses occurring in discs made of metal and composite material were investigated, and the studies were insufficient to investigate the displacements occurring in the discs. Due to the fact that this study contributes to the literature, it is aimed to eliminate this deficiency in the literature by investigating the displacement of the discs. In general, it has been observed that the radial and tangential stresses occurring in discs made of metal and composite material were investigated, and the studies were insufficient to investigate the displacements occurring in the discs. Due to the fact that this study contributes to the literature, it is aimed to eliminate this deficiency in the literature by investigating the displacement of the discs.

1.1. Numerical Methods

In this study, the displacements (displacement) occurring in discs subjected to linear decreasing temperature distribution were investigated numerically. Numerical analysis was performed for 0°C , 45°C , 60°C , 75°C , 90°C and 105°C temperature values. Figure 1 shows the disc subjected to radial displacement. The disk is fixed and its dimensions are taken as $a = 20\text{ mm}$, $b = 40\text{ mm}$.

Figure 1. Numerically analyzed disk.

1.2. Analytical Solution

For a thin disc $=0$ general equilibrium equation [11].

$$r\left(\frac{d\sigma_r}{dr}\right)_i + (\sigma_r)_i = (\sigma_\theta)_i \quad (1)$$

It is given in the form. In equation (1), r is the radius of the disc at any point, here the disc material is

taken as $i = 1$.

$$(\varepsilon_r)_i = \frac{du}{dr} \quad (2)$$

$$(\varepsilon_\theta)_i = \frac{u}{r} \quad (3)$$

Where u is the displacement in the radial direction. Strain-stress relationship;

$$(\varepsilon_r)_i = \frac{1}{E_i}((\sigma_r)_i - (nu)_i(\sigma_\theta)_i) + (\alpha_i)T_r \quad (4)$$

$$(\varepsilon_\theta)_i = \frac{1}{E_i}((\sigma_\theta)_i - (nu)_i(\sigma_r)_i) + (\alpha_i)T_r \quad (5)$$

$$(\sigma_r)_i = F/r \quad (6)$$

$$(\sigma_\theta)_i = \frac{dF}{dr} \quad (7)$$

in the form. If equations (6) and (7) are applied in equations (4) and (5);

$$(\varepsilon_r)_i = \frac{1}{E_i}(F/r - (nu)_i \frac{dF}{dr}) + (\alpha_i)T_r \quad (8)$$

$$(\varepsilon_\theta)_i = \frac{1}{E_i}(\frac{dF}{dr} - (nu)_i F/r) + (\alpha_i)T_r \quad (9)$$

obtained. The fitness equation for elongation;

$$r \frac{d\varepsilon_i}{dr} + \varepsilon_{\theta_i} - \varepsilon_{r_i} = 0 \quad (10)$$

It is obtained. The equilibrium equation where the stress function can be defined as F and equations between (1-7) are used to obtain the general equation (11).

$$r^2 \frac{d^2 F}{dr^2} + r \frac{dF}{dr} - F = -r^2 \alpha_i E_i T_r' \quad (11)$$

1.3. Radial displacements in Linear Increasing Temperature Distribution

Since the discs are different from each other, $i = 1$ for each disk. T_0 is the first temperature value, T_r is the temperature value of any point in the radial direction. If T_r is substituted in equation (11) for stress analysis;

$$r^2 \frac{d^2 F}{dr^2} + r \frac{dF}{dr} - F = -r^2 \alpha_i E_i \frac{T_0}{b-a} \quad (12)$$

he disc exposed to linear decreasing temperature is given below in Figure 2.

$$F = C_1 r^1 + C_2 r^{-1} + A_i r^2 \quad (13)$$

Figure 2. Disc subject to linear increasing temperature distribution.

It is obtained. Radial and tangential stresses,

$$\sigma_r = C_1 r^1 + C_2 r^{-1} + A_i r^2 = \frac{F}{r} \quad (14)$$

$$\sigma_\theta = C_1 r^1 - C_2 r^{-2} + 2A_i r = \frac{dF}{dr} \quad (15)$$

Radial and tangential stresses are written as above. Using the boundary conditions $r=a$ for case $r=b$ for case $\sigma=0$ the integration constants, C_1 , C_2 and the final term A_i are determined as follows:

$$A_i = \frac{E_i \alpha_i T_0}{3(b - a)} \quad (16)$$

$$C_1 = -A_i(a^2 + ab * b^2)/(b + c) \quad (17)$$

$$C_1 = A_i(a^2 b^2)/(a + b) \quad (18)$$

is found as, u : radial displacement is obtained as in (19) below;

$$(U_r)_i = \left(\frac{C_1 r(1 - \text{upsilon}_i)}{E_i} \right) - \left(\frac{C_2 r(1 - \text{upsilon}_i)}{r E_i} \right) + \left(\frac{A_i r^3(3 - \text{upsilon}_i)}{E_i} \right) + \alpha_i r T \quad (19)$$

1.4. Findings And Discussion

In the study; For discs made of ceramic and cast iron materials, thermal stresses from inner surface to outer surface under parabolic increasing temperature distributions were investigated. The disk is fixed and its dimensions are taken as $a= 20$ mm, $b = 40$ mm. Solutions were obtained by using different temperature values of 30°C , 45°C , 60°C , 75°C , 90°C , and 105°C . The material properties of the disc are given in table 1. The analysis result was obtained assuming that the modulus of elasticity does not change with temperature (remains constant).

Table 2 shows the radial displacements that occur inside the discs. Table 3 shows the radial displacements that occur on the outer part of the discs.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of discs [12–16].

Disc No	Disc Materials	E (MPa)	Thermal expansion coefficient (1/ °C)	Poisson Ratio
1	Tungsten carbide (WC)	570000	$4.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.31
2	Boron Carbide (B4C)	472000	$9.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.21
3	Silicon Carbide (SSIC)	420000	$4.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.15
4	Silicon Nitride (Si3N4)	210000	$3.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.22
5	Carbon Glass Fiber	68900	$6.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.27

Table 2. Displacements in the radial direction occurring inside the discs.

Material	r	30 °C	45 °C	60 °C	75 °C	90 °C	105 °C
Tungsten carbide (WC)	r=20	0,052	0,078	0,104	0,130	0,156	0,182
Boron Carbide (B4C)	r=20	0,105	0,158	0,210	0,263	0,315	0,368
Silicon Carbide (SSIC)	r=20	0,050	0,075	0,100	0,125	0,150	0,175
Silicon Nitride (Si3N4)	r=20	0,040	0,060	0,080	0,100	0,120	0,140
Carbon Glass Fiber	r=20	0,069	0,104	0,138	0,173	0,208	0,242
Tungsten carbide (WC)	r=20	0,052	0,078	0,104	0,130	0,156	0,182

Table 3. The radial displacements of the Tungsten carbur disc.

Material	r	30 °C	45 °C	60 °C	75 °C	90 °C	105 °C
Tungsten carbide (WC)	r=40	0,410	0,614	0,819	1,024	1,229	1,434
Boron Carbide (B4C)	r=40	0,831	1,247	1,663	2,078	2,494	2,910
Silicon Carbide (SSIC)	r=40	0,397	0,596	0,795	0,993	1,192	1,391
Silicon Nitride (Si3N4)	r=40	0,317	0,476	0,635	0,793	0,952	1,110
Carbon Glass Fiber	r=40	0,545	0,818	1,091	1,364	1,636	1,909

Figure 3 shows the linear increase of the temperature from the inner region to the outer part of the disc. In the case of boron carbide (B4C), there is displacements in the radial direction formed on the disc. (u= displacements). The radial displacements occurring in the disc with tungsten carbide (WC) material are given in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The radial displacements of the boron carbide (B4C) disc.

The radial displacements occurring in the disc with Boron carbide (B4C) material are given in Figure 4.

Figure 6 shows the radial stress on the silicon nitride (Si3N4) disc

Figure 4. The radial displacements occurring in the disc with Boron carbide (B4C) disc.

Figure 5. Radial displacements in the silicon carbide (SSIC) disc.

Figure 6. The radial displacements in the silicon nitride (Si3N4) disc.

Figure 7 shows the radial stress on the Carbon-Glass disc

In the figures above, the displacements in the radial direction are given in graphs. For example, in the Tungsten carbide (WC) disc, it was observed that 0,052 mm radial displacement occurred in the inner part of the disc at 30 °C, while the radial displacement at the outer part was 0,41 mm. At 45 °C, the radial displacement

Figure 7. The radial displacements in the Carbon/Glass disc.

occurred in the inner part of the Boron Carbide (B4C) (SiC) disc was 0,158 mm, while the radial displacement occurred in the outer part was 1,247 mm. It has been determined that the radial displacement of the inner and outer parts of the silicon nitride (Si3N4) disc is 0,06 mm and 0,476 mm. It has been determined that the radial displacement of the inner and outer parts of the Carbon Glass Fiber disc is 0,104 mm and 0,818 mm. For high temperatures, for example, at 105 °C, the radial displacement that occurs inside the Tungsten carbide (WC) disc is 0,182 mm, while the Boron Carbide (B4C) disc displacement is 0,368 mm. For the radial displacements for the outer parts of the discs; it was observed that the radial displacement occurred on the outer part of the Tungsten carbide (WC) disc was 1,434 mm, and the radial displacement occurred at the outer part of the Boron Carbide (B4C) disc was 2,91 mm. It was determined that the radial displacement occurred in the inner and outer regions of the Silicon Carbide (SSiC) disc was 0,175mm and 1,391 mm, respectively. Internal displacements of Silicon Nitride (Si3N4) and Carbon Glass Fiber discs were calculated as 0.14mm and 0.242mm, respectively. On the outer part of the discs, alternately; It is 1.11 mm and 1.909 mm. In Figure 8, the displacement values occurring on the inner surface of the discs are graphically given.

Figure 8. Displacement values occurring on the inner surface of the discs.

As seen in Figure 8, the displacements occurring in the inner part of the disc from highest to lowest in

order; Boron Carbide (B4C), Carbon Glass Fiber, Tungsten carbide (WC), Silicon Carbide (SSIC) and Silicon Nitride (Si3N4). In Figure 9, the displacement values occurring on the outer surface of the discs are given in graphics.

Figure 9. Displacement values occurring on the outer surface of the discs.

As seen in Figure 9, the displacements occurring in the inner part of the disc from highest to lowest in order; Boron Carbide (B4C), Carbon Glass Fiber, Tungsten carbide (WC), Silicon Carbide (SSIC) and Silicon Nitride (Si3N4). This study is compatible with the studies in the literature. For example, while analyzing the stresses occurring in a layered disc in a different study, it determined the radial displacements in the disc [17, 18]. As is known, discs are used in aerospace industry, aviation industry and sea road transportation vehicles. It is vital to know the displacement occurring in the discs beforehand before assembly. Aluminum and similar metals and materials that are frequently used today have been generally preferred in the studies carried out until today. This study is unique and it reveals that it is very important to investigate the materials that are preferred today, as they are used in critical areas.

2. Conclusion and Recommendations

Since the elasticity modules and thermal expansion coefficients of the materials forming the discs are different, the radial displacements (displacements) are different from each other. Radial displacements occur in the form of shrinkage. As the temperature increases, radial displacements increase. 105 °C; It has been determined that the displacement value occurring at the innermost and outer part of the Boron Carbide (B4C) disc is about 102.1 higher than the Tungsten carbide (WC) disc. 105 °C; It has been determined that the displacement value occurring at the innermost and outer part of the Boron Carbide (B4C) disc is 102.2 percent higher than the Silicon Carbide (SSIC) disc.

105 °C; It has been determined that the displacement value occurring at the innermost part of the Boron Carbide (B4C) disc is 29.9 percent higher than the Silicon Nitride (Si3N4) disc. 105 °C; It was determined that the displacement value occurring at the outermost part of the Boron Carbide (B4C) disc was 162.1 percent higher than the Silicon Nitride (Si3N4) disc. It was determined that the displacement value of the inner part of the Silicon Carbide (SSIC) disc was 24.9 percent higher than the silicon nitride (Si3N4) disc. It was determined that the displacement value occurring at the outermost part of the Silicon Carbide (SSIC) disc was 25.31 percent

higher than that of the Silicon Nitride (Si₃N₄) disc. It was determined that the displacement value of the inner part of the Carbon Glass Fiber disc was 32.9 percent higher than the Tungsten carbide (WC) disc. It was determined that the displacement value of the inner part of the Carbon Glass Fiber disc was 33.1 percent higher than the Tungsten carbide (WC) disc.

When the displacements occurring inside and outside of the materials are examined, it is thought that Silicon Nitride (Si₃N₄) and Silicon Carbide (SSiC) materials have less displacement than other materials, so they may be preferred in designs. Since the displacements occurring in the disc with boron carbide material are high, its use is thought to be disadvantageous compared to other materials in this study. In previous studies, radial and tangential stresses occurring in metal and composite discs were investigated. This study is more applicable than previous studies. The reason for this is that today, materials are easily analyzed with the use of artificial intelligence. Knowing the displacement of Tungsten carbide (WC), Boron Carbide (B₄C) and Carbon / Glass fiber materials at different temperatures is very important in terms of compatibility with other parts to be assembled. This study is thought to be a reference to other studies investigating the stresses and displacements occurring in future discs.

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